

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL DIRECTIONS OF INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH ON THE FORMATION OF CRITICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article provides information on foreign research on the formation of critical thinking and their directions. The views of foreign scientists on the upbringing of thought have been studied from a scientific and theoretical point of view. Instructions on the formation of critical thinking in the scientific research of foreign scientists are presented. This article serves as a methodological resource for the wider scientific community, researchers, and future teachers.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, reaction, foreign scientists, teaching thinking, methods, summarizing, evaluation.*

Introduction

The problems of forming critical thinking have been studied by many foreign scientists and specialists, and today scientific research continues as a relevant pedagogical, psychological, social, and humanistic problem. In particular, scientists from the USA, Russia, France, and India have achieved unique theoretical and methodological results in research in this area. Leading scientists of the USA have created scientific works that include methods for studying, analyzing, and ensuring the development of the critical thinking process, and have tried to expand the possibilities of implementing methods for developing critical thinking in the pedagogical process and applying students' experience in critical thinking in their life activities.

In particular, John Dewey's work "How We Think" puts forward the process of thinking and how to develop it, as well as the implementation of critical thinking in the educational process. In this work, the scholar answers with scientific and practical foundations such questions as what kind of process thinking is, in what state and when it occurs, what factors cause it, and how it develops. He explains that a person should compare the events he has seen, that is, reflect. He stated that the purpose of writing the book "How We Think" is "to take into account the interests and opinions of children in families, to help reduce social problems."

The concept of "Zone of Near Development" (concept ZPD), created by the Russian psychologist Lev Vygotsky, served to reveal important directions in the development of critical thinking in students. Vygotsky defined the zone of proximal development of a child as the developmental interval from the use of the help of adults or experienced peers in solving problems to the ability to perform tasks independently. The ZPD (Zone of Proximal Development) concept is a tool for effectively implementing the connection between learning and mental development in students. A key aspect of Vygotsky's ZPD concept is that a child can fulfill a task only when there is support and communication with a more knowledgeable person.

This concept shows how to help teachers and parents set the most optimal tasks for a child's development, as well as how to contribute to the development of a child's thinking. In his concept,

the scientist relies on scaffolding methods and strategies. These methods imply that the teacher or parent provides temporary assistance to the student in completing the assigned task. As the student's thinking becomes clearly manifested, support for them gradually ceases. This allows students to become more independent.

Within the framework of the ZDP concept, scaffolding provides the following advantages in the process of forming critical thinking in students:

- ✓ fosters confidence: students gain self-confidence as a result of successfully completing difficult tasks with appropriate support;
- ✓ improves problem-solving: students learn to approach complex problems more effectively and independently;
- ✓ develops deep understanding: students achieve deeper problem analysis through scaffolding, i.e., guiding intellectual assistance in forming and expressing their critical opinions about complex situations.

The renowned scholar Richard Paul has conducted numerous studies on critical thinking. In his research, all elements of critical thinking are analyzed more broadly. The scientist explains 12 types of critical thinking, in particular: global, specialized, religious, Socratic, specific, hidden, systematic, episodic, free, limited, natural, and technical.

Richard Paul also worked on the problems of developing critical thinking in collaboration with the renowned pedagogue-psychologist Linda Eldar. Based on the results of their research, Paul and Eldar developed the concept of critical thinking. According to it, critical thinking is carried out in 3 stages:

- observation (formation of knowledge about the problem);
- posing a question (analysis and assessment of the problem);
- finding a solution (making judgments and conclusions about the problem).

Scientists divide these three stages into 6 parts and indicate the direction of implementation:

- knowledge (identification of the main topic or problem);
- understanding (understanding the topic or problem);
- collection of information (examination of information on a topic or problem);
- analysis (study of collected information);
- synthesis (generalization of judgments and attempts at a solution)
- assessment (description and testing of the solution).

Robert Ennis's work "Critical Thinking" reflects the basic principles of critical thinking, research on identifying critical thinking and determining its levels.

Edward Glaser's work "Experiments on the Development of Critical Thinking" reveals the methods of developing critical thinking, the importance of forming critical thinking in the educational process.

Daniel Kahneman's work "Thinking, Fast and Slow" provides information on two types of thinking: quick (intuitive) and slow (logical) thinking, how to reason to avoid mistakes in critical thinking.

Stephen Brookfield's work "Teaching for Critical Thinking" presents pedagogical methods of teaching critical thinking, knowledge aimed at developing students' critical thinking skills.

Diana Halpern's work "Thought and Knowledge: Introduction to Critical Thinking" puts forward ideas about the psychological characteristics of critical thinking, the implementation of thinking and decision-making processes with an understanding.

P.Richard also expressed his well-founded views on critical thinking. He tries to explain that a person's critical thinking skills arise on the basis of their intellectual abilities and personal characteristics. The scientist gives the definition that "critical thinking is not only a manifestation of intellectual ability, but also a striving for the manifestation of the existence of a person".

In the research work "Critical Thinking: How to Prepare Students for a Rapidly Changing World" by Richard Paul and Gerald Nosich, theoretical and practical approaches to the possibilities of applying critical thinking in education and methods of its development were implemented.

Carol Tauris and Elliot Aronson's work "But Not by Me" provides information about the difficulties that a person encounters in admitting their mistakes and guiding them to work on understanding and correcting their mistakes through critical thinking.

One of the well-known scientists, William Graham Sumner, emphasized the importance of critical thinking in the life of society and educational processes. Sumner is a sociologist who considers the formation of critical thinking in people as an important factor in finding solutions to social problems. Sumner, in his book "People's Roads," explains that critical thinking is the basis for organizing a healthy lifestyle for society. According to the scientist, people need to think critically, analyze, and objectively evaluate evidence to make informed decisions. The scientist also emphasizes that education should not consist only of presenting knowledge, facts, and information, but should teach students to think critically and independently based on the acquired knowledge.

B.M.Teplov, considering the levels of human intellect, recognizes that its highest peak is critical thinking. The scientist explains that "critical thinking is the ability to evaluate one's assumptions and abandon them if they do not meet the requirements and do not correspond to logic".

In the works of A.Binet, there are also concepts and explanations of critical thinking, and the scientist showed that critical thinking is thinking based on logic.

The main quality of critical thinking, according to S.A.Korol, is the control of the correspondence of human thought and activity. The scientist cites the following function of critical thinking:

- assessment-verification: this is the function of controlling cognitive activity and comparing acquired knowledge;
- search for new knowledge: this is the function of forming a need for knowledge, ideas, and decisions;
- regulatory: this is a rational analysis of the provided information, the selection of the necessary ones;
- predictive - a function for predicting the results of decisions made and activities.

In his research, S.L.Rubinstein examines thinking as a conscious process of a person. Rubinstein defines critical thinking as "an act of thought that reveals connections leading from the particular to the general and from the general to the particular". In his book "Fundamentals of General Psychology," he puts forward the idea that "in a child, thinking begins with the perception of reality". According to the scientist, "Critical thinking is the process of acquiring new knowledge and experience and analyzing one's mistakes, correcting them, and evaluating the results".

The renowned scientist E. Glaser, within the framework of his research on the topic "Experience in the Development of Critical Thinking," defines critical thinking as "ability". He explains three important characteristics of critical thinking:

- ❖ to calmly consider the causes of the situation, situation, or problem;
- ❖ logical approach;
- ❖ ability to work with evidence

Based on the analysis of the above-mentioned foreign studies and the opinions put forward by scientists, it can be concluded that the formation of critical thinking competencies in students is an important pedagogical necessity for them to have a spiritual worldview, their own point of view and position.

In the table below, we present the direction and content of research conducted by leading foreign scientists on the problems of forming critical thinking.

Author	Work completed		
	Direction	Research title	Researched problem
John Dewey	Socio-pedagogical	"How we think"	The emergence of personality thinking processes and the issue of their proper direction.
Lev Vigotskiy	Psychological-pedagogical	"Thought and Speech"	The process of developing thinking in an individual, the importance of speech and communication in it
S.L.Rubinshteyn	Psychological-pedagogical	"Fundamentals of General Psychology"	Factors and methods of developing thinking in a child
Richard Paul va Gerald Nosich	Socio-pedagogical	"Critical thinking: how to prepare students for a rapidly changing world"	Opportunities for applying critical thinking in education and methods for its development
Diana Halpern	Philosophical-psychological	"Thought and Knowledge: Introduction to Critical Thinking"	Psychological characteristics of thinking, thinking and decision-making processes
Stephen Brookfield	Pedagogical	"Teaching Critical Thinking"	Pedagogical methods of teaching critical thinking, developing students' critical thinking skills through questions

Linda Eldar and Richard Paul	Social- pedagogical	Critical Thinking Competency Standards	Formation of critical thinking skills in students regarding standards, principles, performance indicators and results
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Therefore, critical thinking requires the existence of reason and readiness to apply it, finding logical grounds, and relying on evidence.

Conclusion

In the formation of critical thinking in students, the correct establishment of interpersonal relations, the creation of an atmosphere of cooperation and communication are considered important issues. In the process of interpersonal relationships among students, communication based on cooperation with peers, classmates, teachers, and family members, students have the opportunity to think critically, relying on their existing knowledge and experience.

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